

THE EARTH BELOW

A LOOK AT SATELLITE
REMOTE SENSING

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B N S C

A satellite mosaic of Europe from the NOAA 7 weather satellite. The image shows the continent of Europe and surrounding regions, including parts of North Africa and the Middle East. The colors are processed to resemble natural ones, with green representing vegetation, brown representing urban areas, and blue representing water. The background is a dark blue/black color.

Figure 1. Europe from the NOAA 7 weather satellite

A mosaic made up from a great number of cloud-free scenes sensed over a long period. The image has been processed so that the colours (except for urban areas, which are shown in red) are similar to natural ones.

NRSC

The Earth Below is published by the British National Space Centre as a general introduction to remote sensing.

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'The technique of obtaining information about the Earth's surface and environment from aircraft or satellites.' – Definition of remote sensing.

SPECTRAL SENSITIVITY

There was a time when man had to climb to higher ground for a panoramic view of his environment. Nowadays he no longer needs to: using space technology he gets a far better view. What better vantage point could you ask for than a satellite in orbit? Equip the satellite with sensors to 'see', and computers to process, store and communicate what is seen, and you have the ideal vehicle for monitoring the Earth's surface from space (see Figure 1). In other words, for remote sensing.

Humans are, of course, born remote-sensors: only two of our five senses are based on direct contact with the object sensed, so our knowledge of the world is derived largely from an innate capacity for gathering information from a distance. Indeed one of the principal differences between previous generations and ourselves is the success with which we have used technology to extend this capacity.

Take our dominant sense – sight.

We see because our eyes are capable of making visual sense of rays of sunlight reflected from whatever we are looking at. The rays come in different wavelengths and these we interpret as different colours – the shortest as blue, the longest as red.

However, visible light is not the only form of radiation which occurs on Earth. It is just one constituent of the so-called electromagnetic spectrum (see Figure 4), which extends from gamma rays at one end, through X-rays, ultra-violet rays, visible light and infra-red rays, to microwaves and radio waves at the other. Wavelengths range from one billionth of a centimetre in the case of cosmic rays to kilometres in the case of radio waves.

Obviously, therefore, human remote-sensing capacity is extremely limited – confined to only a very narrow part of the electromagnetic spectrum. Consequently, since we're unlikely ever to acquire the acumen to accept sensory input from the

THE EARTH BELOW A LOOK AT SATELLITE REMOTE SENSING

Figure 2. LANDSAT 4

Figure 3. The past to the present: some satellite operations since 1960.

Figure 4. The electromagnetic spectrum and remote sensing

Gamma rays
Increasing wavelength.

The Electromagnetic Spectrum.

Our knowledge of the world is gained mainly from looking at it – ie, by detecting and interpreting the reflected visible radiation known as light. But visible radiation occupies only a very small part of a whole range of radiation (all travelling at the speed of light, but differing in wavelength) known as the Electromagnetic Spectrum. If we could switch our eyes to sense infra-red and microwave radiation as well as light, we would see things quite differently, for each form of radiation provides different information on the subject viewed. That’s why remote-sensing satellites are usually equipped to detect invisible as well as visible radiation.

Parts of the spectrum used by ‘passive’ satellite sensors.

Passive sensors are sensitive to reflected or emitted radiation. Consequently, if clouds intervene, no radiation from the Earth’s surface will reach them. ‘Active’ systems emit their own pulses of radiation (radar) and record the information reflected back. They can therefore operate night and day, and in all weather conditions.

Sensitive to all visible radiation (ie, light).

Black and white film.

Panchromatic: Sensitive across the visible range.
Orthochromatic: Sensitive to all wavelengths except red.
Special film can detect radiation in the near infra-red.

Colour film.

Uses emulsions sensitive, respectively, to blue, yellow and red.

Spectral signatures.

Different environmental features exhibit different (and distinctive) spectral patterns. Infra-red sensors, for example, can distinguish between healthy and dying plants before the distinction is apparent in the visible bands.

Once the ‘signature’ of a particular type of ground feature is established, it can be used to identify other, like, features.

Windows of transmission.

The atmosphere surrounding the Earth absorbs radiation reflected or emitted by the Earth’s surface. Passive satellite sensors are therefore designed to operate at wavelengths at which absorption is at a minimum – ie, within the so-called ‘windows of transmission’.

‘Bands’ (wavelength ranges) used by satellite sensors.

LANDSAT and SPOT are Earth-observation satellites; NOAA and METEOSAT are meteorological satellites. The latter sense over much wider areas, and use broader bands in the visible and infra-red.

LANDSAT Multispectral Sc

Thematic Mapped

SPOT
(senses either in three bands or in one)

NOAA AVHRR
6-10

METEOSAT

complete range of electromagnetic radiation, we just have to accept second best. Hence our resort to technology as a means of perceiving what would otherwise be invisible to us. For instance, the use of the electron microscope to delve into the substance of the Earth on the microscale; and, of course, the use of satellite remote sensing to examine it on the macroscale.

All surfaces reflect sunlight, but to different degrees; so, depending on the particular surface, certain wavelengths of radiation will be absorbed and others reflected. This explains why some objects look blue to us, some red, and so on. It also explains why different environmental features exhibit different (but distinctive) spectral patterns.

Consequently, once you've established the 'spectral signature' of a particular feature (see 'Classification', page 10), you should be able to use it to identify other like features – always presupposing, of course, that you possess the range of spectral sensitivity and the instant computing power needed to sort out the different wavelengths. Humans aren't equipped to do the job; satellites can be.

SENSING DEVICES

Photography and electronic scanning

There are two main types of remote-sensing device: photographic and electronic-scanning.

Aerial photography is long established as a technique for surveying and mapping. Normally, it records reflected light across the whole of the visible range, but with special film it can also pick up a certain amount of infra-red radiation (the so-called 'near infra-red') at wavelengths just outside the visible.

Its advantage for remote sensing is its very high resolution – its ability to register small objects from hundreds of kilometres up in space. Its disadvantage is its limited spectral range, and the problem, in an unmanned satellite, of getting the exposed film back to earth.

The photographic camera records a complete scene every time the shutter clicks (see Figure 5). Electronic scanners construct their images unit by unit, scanning

consecutive strips of ground in lines at right angles to the flight path or orbit, as in Figure 6. And, since the information collected is recorded in electronic form, it's a relatively easy matter to radio it down to ground stations for reconstitution into computer-generated images.

Where electronic scanners really come into their own, though, is in the width and selectivity of their spectral ranges. Multispectral scanners, for example, can be built to sense radiation in any waveband (a band is a specific range of wavelengths: see Figure 4) in the visible and infra-red; and, of course, each band carries different information on the ground below. On the debit side, their resolution isn't at present all that good, so don't expect them to collect information from space on any feature less than about 10 metres across in real-life size.

Passive and active

Remote-sensing devices which just point their sensors at the Earth and, as it were, sit waiting for the information to come up to them (ie, all of those so far discussed) are called passive. Those that don't are called active. And that classification brings us to radar.

Sensors recording radiation in the visible and infra-red bands have one great problem: the weather. If clouds intervene, no radiation from the Earth's surface will reach them.

A radar-based system gets round this problem by simply ignoring it – or at least by ignoring the visible and infra-red as sources of information. It generates its own pulsed beam of radiation (which can 'see' through clouds), directs this on successive strips of the terrain below, and registers the information reflected back. Radar therefore is an all-weather system, and, because it's not dependent on sunlight, effective night or day.

Figures 7 and 11 were derived from information collected by SEASAT, a short-lived, but very successful, active-sensing satellite launched in 1978, primarily for sea-area observations.

Figure 7. Active remote-sensing. A SEASAT mosaic

SEASAT's radar altimeter recorded distances from the satellite to the sea's surface. The distances were found to vary by as much as 200m, mirroring, in a subdued form, the relief of the sea floor.

1. The Mid-Atlantic Ridge.
2. Fracture zones associated with the Ridge.
3. The Kuril, Marianas and Tonga Trenches.
4. The Hawaiian island chain.
5. The Emperor Seamounts.

Figure 5. The Red Sea. An oblique photo from a manned satellite
 Cameras have been used by orbiting astronauts since 1962. Dramatic as many of the photographs are, though, the scattering of blue light by the atmosphere means that they convey less information than multispectral scanners. NASA

Figure 6. Passive data acquisition
 Satellite imagery can be formed using either the tilting-mirror linescanner, as with LANDSAT, or by the 'push-broom' solid-state scanner which records each line of radiation instantaneously.

SEASAT was the first satellite to use a high-resolution radar imaging instrument. It was also equipped with a radar scatterometer which measured surface-wind speed and direction, a radar altimeter which measured ocean-wave heights, and a visible and infra-red radiometer for determining sea-surface temperatures and cloud-cover.

ORBITS, RECORDING AND TRANSMITTING

Orbits

How does the satellite gather, record and send information back to Earth? Obviously, the starting point is the part of the Earth the satellite is over. And that means orbits.

Remote-sensing satellites use two main types of orbit: geo-stationary and polar.

Geo-stationary satellites (see Figure 8) are put into orbit 35,900 km directly above the equator. At this altitude the speed of the satellite exactly matches the Earth's rotation. To all intents and purposes, therefore, the satellite is geo-stationary – hovering continuously over the same part of the Earth. Consequently, geo-stationary satellites are used either to transmit telecommunications signals or to get a very broad view of the weather.

Polar orbits (see Figure 8) are lower in altitude – 600-1500 km above the Earth. In a polar orbit a satellite follows a North-South path close to the poles, and gradually traverses every part of the Earth over a period of days. It then starts the same cycle again, and, since in effect it constantly retraces its steps, it is ideally placed to view and monitor environmental changes. Seasonal rhythms, for example, or short-term events (floods, forest fires, pollution, and the like) or changes in land-use patterns in farming and urban areas.

The second generation American LANDSAT satellites (see Figures 2, 8 and 9) return to the same point on the globe every 16 days. The orbits are sun-synchronous, so, whenever the satellites cross the Equator, it's always about 09.45 local time on the ground below.

This detailed monitoring of the Earth's surface has been going on since 1972, and the amounts of data involved are mind-boggling: 5000 scenes a month from LANDSAT 1 and 2

Figure 8. Orbits: polar and geo-stationary

Figure 9. The LANDSAT reference system
Each orbit ('path') of LANDSAT 4 and 5 is numbered, and so is every image taken along each path. This system therefore provides a set of co-ordinates ('path' and 'row') for identifying any image.

Figure 10. SPOT's options

France's SPOT satellite senses in three bands in the visible and near infra-red, and has greatly improved resolution. But what makes it so innovative are its tilting sensors, which allow it to take a sideways look at areas which it has already visited or is about to visit.

With fixed vertical sensors SPOT would have been able to view an area only when directly above it – ie, once every 26 days. With tilting sensors it can view an area much more frequently: 98 times a year at the Equator and 154 times at 45 degrees North.

The advantages in terms of frequency of viewing are obvious. But that's not all. Since the satellite can now sense the same area from two angles, it has the facility to produce stereoscopic pairs, and hence the capacity to provide a new form of remote-sensing information: relief data.

Figure 11. SEASAT image of wave patterns off the Shetlands

At the other end of the scale from Fig. 7 this image shows wave patterns in a small area.

alone, each scene built up from 30,000,000 items of information. But no doubt you'd be more impressed by that statement if you knew what was meant by an 'item'.

Recording and transmitting the information

Take a close look at a picture in a newspaper, and you'll see that it consists of a pattern of different-sized dots. The same technique is used to produce a television image, though in this case the dots vary in brightness, reproducing the reflected light recorded by the television camera.

A satellite image is not all that different from a TV picture, for both are built up and reproduced electronically from dot-like picture elements – from so-called 'pixels'.

Since the pixel is the smallest item of information registered by the sensors on a satellite, it determines the resolution of the image: and, obviously, any feature on the Earth's surface smaller than the area encompassed by a pixel will not be seen as an entity in itself.

Figure 12 shows you what we mean. The upper picture represents a 15 km × 15 km area extracted from a scene recorded by the scanner on the latest of the American satellites, LANDSAT 5. In the lower pictures, part of this image has been enlarged to delineate the pixels, and hence the limits of resolution (in this case 30 m × 30 m). Anyone walking on the beach in this scene would occupy only about one two-thousandth of the pixel area, and obviously wouldn't be detected by the sensor even if his or her clothes were very different in reflectance from the surroundings. The best resolution at present – 10 m × 10 m – is available from SPOT (see Figure 10), a French Earth-sensing satellite launched in 1986.

At the other extreme, meteorological satellites looking at cloud systems operate over extremely broad fields of view, and have very low resolutions; indeed they sacrifice resolution in order to achieve the required daily coverage of the whole globe. And, given a scanning swath as wide as 3000 km (as is the case with the NOAA satellites), a pixel size of 1.1 km is not all that bad. Europe's METEOSAT weather satellite has a resolution of 2.4 km.

Whatever the size of the pixel, however, the recording procedure is the same.

As the satellite does its line-by-line scan of the ground below, it senses the average intensity of

radiation (the so-called 'spectral reflectance') from each pixel-sized area in turn, and records it as a digital number – ie, a binary number consisting of combinations of 0s and 1s. And, of course, it goes through the same procedure for all the bands in which the satellite is sensing. Each pixel is therefore represented by a digital number.

Digital numbers are used merely to convert the information into a form which can be transmitted, handled, processed, stored and retrieved by computer. Depending on the strength of signal received in each spectral band, the pixels are allocated a number from 0 to 255 – a scale which fits easily into the operational needs of the computer. Since each spectral band 'sees' in monochrome, zero is taken as representing black, and 255 white; and between these two there is a sequence of 254 numbers representing different tones of grey.

The remote-sensing satellite radios this information to the ground station in a stream of binary numbers. If it's not in line of sight of the station, it either stores it on a tape recorder and waits until it is, or relays it via a communications satellite.

PROCESSING THE INFORMATION

To reconstitute the images from the data transmitted by the satellite, the ground-station's computers merely decode the binary data and allocate the appropriate tone to each pixel. The images can then be displayed on a monitor screen or as a printout. They will, however, be monochrome (as in Figure 13), and they will be very raw and very basic. Hence the need for computer processing.

Some of the main techniques for this are outlined below.

Geometric transformation

The data has first to be corrected for Earth-curvature, Earth-rotation and satellite-attitude errors. However, even when this has been done, the images will still contain geometric distortions, with the centre of the scene located to an accuracy of only a few kilometres.

To improve this accuracy, a sufficient number of ground control points (ie, headlands, dams, airfields, and so on, which are readily

Figure 12 . Weymouth, 26 April 1984

Unlike the Devon scene in Fig. 14, this LANDSAT image has been processed to produce a 'natural-colour' composite. The band 1 data (which was not used in the false-colour composite) has been projected as blue, band 2 as green and band 3 as red; ie, the information from the different bands has been fed to the three colour guns in the monitor, and projected in the colours in which we normally see the frequency ranges concerned. The zoom effect shows how images are built up from pixels. NRSC

Figure 13. Devon band by band

Data from bands 1, 2, 3 and 4 of LANDSAT's thematic mapper sensor, 26 April 1984. In each case, the information is shown as a monochrome image: ie, in the form the satellite senses it – as variations on a 256-level grey scale. Each band allows us to see the area in slightly different ways, depicting land-water boundaries in one case, vegetation differences in another, and so on. NRSC

Figure 14. Devon: false-colour composite

This composite was produced by projecting band 2 information as blue, band 3 as green and band 4 as red. Since our eyes can't see radiation in the near infra-red, band 4 has to be simulated – given a colour.

In this scene reds indicate growing plants, and, the month being April, most of the lower ground is dominated by this colour. Dartmoor is higher, wetter and cooler, and is shown as blue – plant growth hasn't started yet. The darker magenta and brown patches are woodland. The blue-white areas north-east of Plymouth are the china-clay pits of Lea Moor. NRSC

identifiable both on the image and on a map) are selected for calculation of a least-squares fit, and the results are then used to adjust the image to the map co-ordinates.

Contrast stretching

Remote-sensing satellites have to cope with an extremely wide variety of terrains: anything from 'shiny' ice-caps and deserts, to 'dark' forests. Not surprisingly, therefore, their sensors are designed to respond to an extremely wide range of spectral radiation. This, however, has its disadvantages, for within a given locality the variation in terrain will not be all that great on a particular day, and will therefore take up only a narrow part of the sensor's total range. As a result, the image recorded for that locality will tend to be even-toned and murky.

The image processor's answer to this is to spread the recorded reflectance values across the whole of the tonal range available, so that the distinction between tones becomes much more pronounced. In other words, the computer treats the minimum reflectance value of the pixels present in the image as 0, the maximum as 255, and then stretches out the rest, maintaining the shape of the reflectance distribution curve (as in Figure 15), but widening the 'tonal gaps' between the values.

The result is a much more contrasting image. Hence the name 'contrast stretching'.

Density slicing

Even after contrast stretching, however, the human eye might be unable to distinguish the gradations between 256 different tones, and so could find it difficult to recognise the features present. One way out of this is to delineate the different features by colour coding: ie, to get the computer to use colours to characterise areas with similar densities of reflectance.

The standard way of 'colour coding' (see Figure 16) is to choose a particular spectral band (the infra-red is best for the purpose), take a series of slices across the image, and assign a colour to the particular group of digital numbers representing a particular key feature. Eight slices, for example, mean eight different key features and eight different colours.

If you then apply the chosen 'colour coding' over the entire image, you get a rough classification into similar and contrasting cover features. And, since the computer knows the number of pixels in each feature, and

the area covered by a pixel, it will, if you ask it, also calculate the area covered by the different features.

Colour composites

A simpler way of using colour is to select three spectral bands and feed the data from each through a different colour gun on the image processor's monitor. What you end up with then is either a natural-colour or a false-colour composite.

A natural-colour composite is what it says it is: an image whose features are depicted in the colours we associate with them. For example, a LANDSAT natural-colour composite is produced (see Figure 12) by projecting bands 1, 2 and 3 (blue, green and red) through the image-analysis computer's blue, green and red guns, respectively.

But how about information sensed in bands beyond the visible range (eg, the near or middle infra-red); how do you represent that in colour?

Obviously there's only one way: arbitrarily. Hence the use of the adjective 'false' for colours which have no other function than to simulate radiation that can't be seen. In LANDSAT's case, a false-colour composite (see Figure 14) is normally produced by projecting bands 2, 3 and 4 (or bands 3, 4 and 5) as blue, green and red.

Most of the composites reproduced in this booklet were processed as just described, but that's not to say that the colours might not have been employed in a different way for a different purpose. Figure 22 is a case in point.

In general, therefore, it's no use asking what the colours 'mean'. What they mean depends on the satellite concerned, its sensors, the spectral bands used, the time of year at which the information was sensed, and the way in which it was subsequently processed.

Classification

Most users will want to classify the imagery into different kinds of ground cover. To do this the image-analysis computer first establishes the characteristic 'spectral signatures' of the features concerned (see page 4 and Figure 17), and then uses these to seek out like features.

In other words, once you've 'trained' it to recognise various signatures on a small test site, you can identify features with similar signatures right across the image. You then have a method which allows you

Figure 17. Classification in South-West London

An example of spectral classification, carried out on a GEMS interactive image-analysis computer.

This technique is an important tool in land-use mapping. The first step was to generate a single-band scene and enlarge it. The cursor was then moved on to a target (in this case, an area of Richmond Park known to contain deciduous trees), and the GEMS was told to remember the 'spectral signature' of the pixels in this area. The same training process was repeated for other known deciduous-tree areas, and finally the computer was told to find every other group of pixels with the same spectral signature and display them as yellow.

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Figure 15. Contrast stretching

Two LANDSAT thematic-mapper band-4 images of Romney Marsh on 21 October 1984. The one on the left is unstretched.

Problem:
Human eye unable to distinguish subtle changes in tones for individual pixels.

Grey scale for a single band scene

Solution:
Slice corresponding to a significant type of feature on the image (eg, estuarine water depth, crop type, vegetation cover) selected and displayed in colour on an image processing computer.

All pixels with this range of values assume the same colour.

Further slices selected to complete the 'colour coding'.

Figure 16. Density slicing

Unprocessed, satellite images are monochrome – made up of 256 different tones of grey allocated to reflect the different intensities of radiation recorded by the sensor. The features present in monochrome images are therefore difficult to distinguish visually. Density slicing is the technique used to overcome the problem.

Density slicing is essentially colour coding. You use the image processor to take 'slices' across regions of the image with significant ground features, you assign a different colour to represent the different combinations of grey tones characterising each feature, and you tell the processor to apply the codings over the whole image.

Figure 18. Poole Harbour and the Purbeck Hills, 9 August 1984

Land-use patterns show up well. The poorer soil conditions to the south and west of the harbour support only heathland vegetation. The richer soils to the north-west support intensive arable farming; the blue areas indicate bare-soil conditions, possibly after harvest. The underlying geology has obviously influenced the scale and pattern of the fields between the chalk ridge and Corfe Castle, the clay belt in the valley to the west of Swanage, and the higher limestone plateau on the southern coastline.

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not only to map and measure extremely large areas of land with the minimum of on-site verification, but also to identify target areas not detectable before processing.

Establish the spectral characteristics of a particular crop, and the computer will print out and measure the entire area of crop covered by the image. Undertake the same exercise on another date, and you can determine any changes in land usage. Establish the spectral signatures associated with the occurrence of a particular mineral, and you can identify new sites for exploration.

Geographic Information System (GIS)

It is important to recognise that satellite data on its own can rarely provide the complete answer, and that the techniques described above are only examples of the wide range available. One effective way of improving data-usability is through the GIS.

With GIS techniques remote-sensing imagery can be integrated with a wide range of other data, and as a result images are now becoming a valuable and readily accessible source of information for the geologist, land-use planner and environmentalist. In other words, GIS is an area of application in which major progress can be expected.

In its simplest form it can be used to overlay map data (eg, parish boundaries) on to a remote-sensing image, or to mask off a particular area of an image for analysis. In a more sophisticated application, the UK's National Remote Sensing Centre has used it to demonstrate its potential for identifying areas in North East Scotland satisfying specific requirements for housing development (see Figure 19).

APPLICATIONS

Remote sensing is already accepted as a basic working tool in meteorology, and as a tool with considerable scope in agriculture, damage assessment, geology, hydrology, land-use mapping, regional mapping, ecology, marine operations, and pollution monitoring.

Its applications are numerous and expanding. Judged by the variety of satellites which will soon be flying,

the increasing range and sensitivity of their sensors, and the sophisticated image-processing and -interpreting facilities now available, remote sensing looks very ready to take off.

In meteorology the main application is, of course, weather forecasting. But weather satellites can also keep an eye on marine pollution (eg, oil slicks), and their sea-temperature measurements are useful in predicting movements of fish. Again, combine weather data (eg, on drought and wind stress) with Earth-sensing data on crop acreages, and you have a base from which to increase the accuracy of harvest-yield predictions.

Geology has been one of remote sensing's most fruitful fields – not surprisingly, for satellites are, after all, perfectly placed to supply data contributing to a quick, economical and comprehensive appraisal of geological structure. Multi-band sensing can reveal faulting and lineaments, the distribution of mineral-rich zones, and vegetation effects associated with underlying base-metal deposits or leakage of volatiles from oil-fields.

Then there's land-use mapping, soil mapping and terrain analysis. In many developing countries the relatively low cost of remote sensing has transformed the approach to these. And the same goes for crop monitoring, damage assessment (eg, flooding, storms), snow and vegetation-growth monitoring (important for hydrological models and crop management), and the detection of soil-moisture conditions conducive to locust breeding.

The sea also has its remote-sensing applications. Three brief examples: satellites are excellent monitors of coastal pollution (sewage and sludge); infra-red images of clear shallow sea can be processed to provide a cheap substitute for a marine survey; and active remote sensing can help improve accuracy in forecasting wave patterns and heights in the open ocean. This last will be of considerable practical value, for adding a metre to the height of an offshore platform adds £1 million to its cost, and ship-route planning based on up-to-date information on wave patterns can reduce sailing times, and hence energy and money.

Finally, education. Satellite images are creating interest at all levels in this field – not only in illustrating geographical patterns, relationships and concepts, but also in fostering environmental awareness.

Figure 19. Geographic Information System (GIS)

Geographic Information Systems integrate remote-sensing data with each other and with other forms of information (eg, cartographic) in ways which add to the usefulness of each.

In a project to demonstrate their practical potential the UK's National Remote Sensing Centre used GIS techniques to identify suitable sites for housing development in a particular area of North-East Scotland.

To be suitable, sites had to be i) on land, ii) less than 150 m high, iii) relatively flat (any slope had to be less than 1:50), and iv) within 3 km of an A-class road. The images used – a LANDSAT Band 7 image taken in April 1981, digital terrain models of height and slope, and an image of distance from A roads – are shown on the left.

The range of digital values indicating sites satisfying the individual criteria was first determined for each image, and then, using classification techniques, these values were combined to identify sites meeting all four requirements (ie, sites potentially suitable for housing development).

Figure 20. Desert terrain in Oman

Some of the best remote-sensing images come from cloud-free arid zones, where the geological structure is often superbly exposed. In this LANDSAT scene, however, the wind-moulded dune forms dominate the terrain, and bedrock is invisible. Huntings

Figure 21 . East Anglia: land use

LANDSAT thematic-mapper images for 14 May 1984 and 6 July 1984. The enlargements illustrate the potential of satellite remote sensing for crop monitoring. Notice how well individual fields stand out. Huntings

Figure 22, Kenya, Rift Valley.
LANDSAT 5 thematic-mapper
scene, 30 July 1984

Images like the one above are becoming of increasing importance in the developing countries, for they allow resources and land use to be rapidly assessed over a large area, and can therefore play a vital role in planning the rural economy.

This area lies 250km NNW of Nairobi, and is 185km across. Band 3 data has been processed to appear as blue, band 5 green, and band 4 red.

The Rift Valley is on the left, running vertically down the image, its floor covered with barren salty sediments (white tones). The thin red vein denotes the presence of vegetation along the river which flows into Lake Baringo (black) at the bottom of the image.

A series of faults can be seen on the

western wall of the rift. There are also signs of volcanism, linked to the rift faulting, in the form of circular volcanic plugs. The fault scarp bordering the rift is being eroded, and fans of debris (grey tone) can be seen bordering the saline flats, especially on the west of the valley.

To the right of the rift is part of the plateau. At this time of the year, and with this image processing, the savanna grassland is seen as white tones, and the woodland along the watercourses as red dendritic patterns on the right centre of the scene. The red shading on the eastern slope of the rift indicates vegetation growth, and the richer red at the top right is forest on higher and moister sites.

Lateritic soils are rich in iron oxide, and in this image are recorded in a number of locations as green.

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Figure 23. Iceland, 13 July 1978

Monitoring remote areas and their environmental changes is an important use of remote sensing.

This LANDSAT false-colour composite shows (top, white) the southern part of the Vatnajökull ice cap, with its outlet glaciers (light blue) reaching down to lower ground. The outwash plains (black) are crossed by braiding streams whose high sediment load gives them a blue colour. The sediment can be seen spreading out along the shoreline, which would otherwise be rather indistinct. The red areas indicate plant growth (grasses), and the Laki volcanic fissure can be seen on the left.

NRSC

Figure 24. Siberian sea ice

This LANDSAT image provided confirmation of the arctic shipping crisis of 1983, when ice almost trapped 41 ships using the Northern Sea Route. The icebreaker tracks can be clearly seen.

CCRS

**Figure 25. London from SPOT,
30 June 1986**

A highly detailed colour composite produced by combining images derived from all four of SPOT's spectral bands: the panchromatic (10m resolution) and the three multi-bands (20m resolution).

Some landmarks: Regent's Park is top left. Lord's cricket ground is further left, with (because of the different spectral properties of short and long grass) the centre strips clearly visible. The Oval and its gasholders are just south of the Thames, to the right of Vauxhall Bridge. Euston Station, with its highly reflective glass roof, is the large whiteish complex to the right of Regent's Park. The Tower of London, Tower Bridge and HMS Belfast are clearly visible top right. Oxford Street, the Strand and Aldwych are also easy to find.

Copyright CNES SPOT

**Figure 26. Stubble burning,
6 September 1985**

*Remote sensing is a practical way of
discovering the extent of stubble burning.
This image is from a NOAA satellite's
AVHRR sensor. Burns are depicted as dark
spots, representing warmer ground.*

Dundee University

**Figure 27. Snow-covered Derbyshire,
13 January 1982**

*A LANDSAT 2 image, with Derby centre
right. LANDSAT 2 had a resolution of 80m,
so detail is far less complete than in the
SPOT scene in Fig. 25. The relief effect
created by the shadows cast by the early
morning sun is particularly noticeable
because of the snow cover. The northward
driit of the plumes from the power-station
cooling tower is also distinctive.* NRSC

**Figure 28. Djebel Armour, Algeria,
23 February 1986**

In this arid terrain the complex eroded fold structures of the Atlas Mountains show up in fine detail. A series of parallel anticlines and synclines, some with a closed-dome structure, stretches from the Sahara Desert margin, bottom right, to the mountains, top left.

The drainage pattern of dry wadis and gullies, and the alluvial fans are clearly visible, as are small patches of vegetation (bright red) along some of the water courses. An irrigation scheme can be seen on the extreme right. The shades of red and pink on the higher and moister mountains denote a cover of grass and forest. Bare rock and stony areas are represented by blues and greens, and the yellow and white shades are sand and alluvial deposits without vegetation.

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THE FUTURE

What will the future bring to remote sensing? One thing is certain: interest will grow, and many more countries will become actively involved.

METEOSAT, GOES, METEOR, TIROS-N – weather satellites will, of course, continue into the future.

On the Earth-resources front, the 1970s were dominated by the American LANDSAT satellites, to be joined in the 1980s by satellites from France, Japan and India. For the 1990s a lengthy list of launches are proposed. Some satellites (eg, LANDSAT and SPOT) will continue and upgrade current series, others will be part of the new era of microwave satellites, the first of which will be the European Space Agency's ERS-1 (see Figure 29) with mainly radar-based sensors. It will concentrate on the ocean, coastal zones and polar regions, and will be equipped to measure surface wind speed and direction, wave heights and structures, sea temperatures, and ocean currents.

Commercial recognition of the importance of remote sensing is

another pointer to the future. For example, responsibility for LANDSAT passed from NASA to the Eosat Corporation in 1986, and SPOT has been a government-funded commercial project from the start.

Finally, the US Government's invitation to other countries to participate in the development of an international space station is also significant for the future. Under the European Space Agency's Columbus programme, Britain is heavily involved in the preparatory work, with the main focus on the polar platforms – permanent structures in low Earth orbit (see Figure 30). Their first use is likely to be for the deployment of an extensive suite of instruments for remote sensing the Earth's surface and atmosphere.

In the 1990s, then, billions of bytes of data will no doubt be beaming down from a whole range of much more sophisticated satellites. Obviously a decade for the scientific, environmental and commercial world to look forward to.

Figure 29. An artist's impression of the ERS-1 satellite

Figure 30. An artist's impression of the Polar Platform

Figure 31. Really-remote remote sensing: the red spot of Jupiter and one of its moons

This moon (Io by name) was one of the first of the heavenly bodies to be discovered through the telescope – and by Galileo, no less, in 1610. Some 369 years later, Voyager 1 took a closer look and sent back some of the most beautiful remotely sensed images ever recorded.

NASA

WHERE TO GET A SATELLITE IMAGE?

The answer to that depends on needs and budget. Remote-sensing data is published in various forms: images and tapes, obviously, but also posters, slide sets and videos.

Specialist users can get tapes and images (and, of course, information) from the National Remote Sensing Centre at the address given below. Companies which supply and interpret imagery as a service can be contacted through the British Association of Remote Sensing Companies.

Several specialist books explaining the principles of remote sensing have been published, and imagery is used in many books for general illustration, and is the specific focus of a smaller number.

As an alternative to the above, you could, of course, always have a go at producing your own images. Budget systems for receiving meteorological satellite data are on the market.

MORE INFORMATION

**National Remote Sensing Centre,
Royal Aerospace Establishment,
Farnborough, Hampshire GU14 6TD.
Tel: 0252 541464.**

Information on remote sensing.
Images, slide sets, videos, posters.

**European Space Agency,
Publications Division,
ESTEC – PB 299, 2200 AG,
Noordwijk, Netherlands.**

Earth Observation Quarterly
(available free).

**British Association of Remote
Sensing Companies,
PO Box 201,
Northampton.**

Trade association of companies
involved in remote sensing.

**Remote Sensing Society,
c/o Department of Geography,
University of Nottingham,
Nottingham NG7 2RD.**

Tel: 0602 506101.
Learned society.

**Geographical Association,
343 Fulwood Road,
Sheffield S10 3BP.
Tel: 0742 661666.**

Articles, and slide and book reviews,
in 'Geography' and 'Teaching
Geography'. The Association's
Satellite Remote Sensing Working
Group is examining the educational
use of remote sensing.

**The British National Space Centre is
Britain's space agency, directing civil
space activities and developing future
policy.**

**For further information on BNSC's
remote sensing and other
programmes, contact:**

**The Information Office
British National Space Centre
Millbank Tower
Millbank
London SW1P 4QU
Tel: 01-217 4290 or 4289**

Figure 32. The Chernobyl area: a LANDSAT 5 image taken on 29 April 1986, 3 days after the nuclear-reactor accident

A composite based on Bands 3, 4 and 5. Images like this have been used to assess the thermal changes in and around Chernobyl. The reactors are sited next to the cooling-water basins (arrowed), and water from these is taken from the Pripyak River and circulated anti-clockwise around the central dike of the 15-km reservoir to dissipate the heat.

NRSC

